

Experiment design task 2 - Group 15

Gunnar Sjúrdarson Knudsen
Matriculation Number: 12028205

Guillermo Alamán Requena
Matriculation Number: 11937906

Paul Joe Maliakel
Matriculation Number: 12012422

ABSTRACT

This paper is part of a submission for the course **188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science**, where we were to select three recent research papers, and estimate their reproducibility. Furthermore we were asked to dive in depth into one of the papers, and attempt to recreate their result. For this we chose the paper "Cross-Lingual Document Retrieval Using Regularized Wasserstein Distance" by Balikas et al. [5]. Following is our results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Our report is organized as follows: sections 2 and 3 describe the approaches of our selected papers and compares the likelihood of each them to be reproduced. Sections 4 and 5 describe the experimental setup, code and workflow of the chosen paper: [12]. Section 6 focuses on the difficulties encountered when trying to reproduce the results claimed in [5]. Sections 7 and 8 focus on the key findings from our work and the steps carried out to reproduce the experiments from [5]. The results gotten are shown in section 9. Finally, section 11 concludes and proposes further work.

2 SELECTION OF SCIENTIFIC PAPERS AND REPRODUCIBILITY ASSESSMENT

In this task, we were asked to select 3 candidate datasets from the proceedings of the past 5 years of three conference series (SIGIR, CIKM and ECIR). [12], [5] and [7] were selected for this purpose. We tried to choose 3 candidates as diverse as possible from an experimental design point of view.

[12] got our attention right away. The issue of detecting fake news is of high relevance nowadays and the approach in this paper to do so was very interesting for us. However, although the method is described in a very detailed manner, many important aspects are missing for reproducibility. On what regards the data, the sources are named (Twitter and Weibo) but specific instructions on how to get the data, train and test splits, dimensions and other features are ignored. Instead a summary of statistics of the datasets is provided. On what regards the code, there is a wide description of the classification models used, including software employed (Theano) and GPU. Nevertheless, the description of the feature extraction task is very ambiguous due to the lack of specific data sources. We consider this paper as **very unlikely to be reproduced with the information provided by the authors**.

[5] proposes a cross-lingual document retrieval method that improves several baselines in terms of Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR). This is a more technical task, however in terms of **reproducibility** we consider it much more **feasible**. Code and data are provided in GitHub.

[7] focuses on genre and popularity prediction of songs using their lyrics. For that purpose, they use a dataset with around 400.000 songs in English. **The only indication about the provenance of those songs is that they were retrieved from "user-generated content on the Web."** What is more, they specify that an extensive preprocessing was performed to remove text that is not part of the lyrics and to remove duplicate lyrics. However, the source code of the mentioned preprocessing is neither provided. The labels for the genre and popularity classification are taken from [10] ([4] in the original paper). In that paper, several databases are cited and we were not able to know exactly from which of them the data was obtained. Nevertheless, they explain that only a subset of the 400.000 song samples was used to avoid class-imbalance problems. Indications on which samples were included in that subset are missing. On what respects the modelling part, four traditional machine learning algorithms are used for training and prediction (SVM, KNN, Random Forest and Genre Vectors) and three types of neural networks (CNN, GRU and Bi-GRU). Apart from the **lack of source code**, a lot of information is missing about the implementation of these methods (programming language, interpreter, packages...) and very little information is provided about the hyperparameter set-up for each of the algorithms. For all of this, we consider that it is **very unlikely to reproduce the exact results gotten by this paper**. The only thing that could be tried is to reproduce the method using different data and implementation and check the correctness of the hypothesis via a different, approach as suggested in [11].

3 COMPARISONS OF THREE PAPERS

When assessing the likelihood of reproducibility, we labelled our selected papers [12], [5] and [7] as "borderline impossible", "moderate" and "hard" respectively (See table 1). The difference between [5] and [7] is basically the technical difficulty of the approach. The implementation of the later one is, in our opinion, easier to replicate (existing packages and likely to have been coded in python). What is more, when building a dataset with song lyrics, many of them may coincide with the original data (or at least contain the same kind of content), whereas choosing the same samples from Twitter and Weibo seems less likely. [12] provides, as mentioned before, source code and data to be replicated. Since we prefer to focus on experimentation and exact reproduction of the results shown in the paper, **we chose this paper for the main task**. Although, as said, the experimental setup and implementation are documented enough for reproducibility, our attempt to replicate the results will show some of the challenges of reproducibility that are faced nowadays, specially from the programming perspective. For that reason, we labelled it as "moderate" instead of "easy."

Paper	[12]	[5]	[7]
Year	2017	2018	2019
Journal	CIKM	ECIR	ECIR
Available data	No	Yes	No
Available code	Description only	Yes	No
Difficulty	Borderline impossible	Moderate	Hard

Table 1: Reproducibility comparison

4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, we are going to describe the experimental setup designed in our chosen paper [5].

4.1 Data

4 bilingual Wikipedia datasets are extracted from Wikipedia corpora of linguatools. The chosen languages for the experiment are French, German, Greek and Finnish and they are all paired with their corresponding Wikipedia documents in English. Each dataset has 10000 documents, from which 9500 are used for training and 500 for evaluation of the approaches. In the source code, a help script is provided to get exactly the same data as the one used for the experiment (for the English-French Wikipedia documents).

4.2 Preprocessing

In the preprocessing steps, they lowercase the documents, remove stop-words, punctuation symbols and numbers and keep only the first 500 words of each document.

4.3 Models

In this section, they present the models used in this paper for **cross-lingual information retrieval**. We can differentiate between those models used as baseline: term-frequency (tf), inverse document frequency (idf), neural bag of words (nBOW) and bilingual Latent Dirichlet Allocation (BiLDA). And, on the other hand, those introduced as **novelties in this paper that extend the Word Mover’s Distance (WMD) method by incorporating different weighting schemes and using a regularized version of the Wasserstein Distance**. They are called Wass and Entro_Wass. Note that, there are two versions for each of them depending on whether they use tf or idf to produce the high-dimensional source and target histograms.

4.4 Results

For the evaluation, Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) is used. This metric shows the rank of the correct answer in the returned documents. Naturally, the higher the MRR, the better the method used.

As we mentioned above, there are 4 bilingual datasets. This allows actually for **8 different experiments since each of them gives two retrieval problems**: retrieve documents in English using queries in a second language and vice-versa. What is more, for each of the models they experiment with 3 kind of systems to overcome the language difference: those that rely on translations,

those that rely on cross-lingual embeddings and those which first handle out-of-vocabulary (OOV) words and then use cross-lingual embeddings. Thus, the scope of results to be reproduced that are summarized in 1 is very broad.

	En→Fr	Fr→En	En→Ge	Ge→En	En→Gr	Gr→En	En→Fi	Fi→En
Systems that rely on topic models								
BiLDA	.559	.468	.560	.536	.559	.508	.622	.436
Systems that rely on translations								
tf	.421	.278	.287	.433	.441	.054	.068	.025
idf	.575	.433	.478	.516	.535	.126	.081	.028
nBOW _{tf}	.404	.276	.378	.440	.531	.132	.329	.042
nBOW _{idf}	.550	.488	.449	.509	.577	.256	.398	.081
Wass _{tf}	.704	.691	.620	.655	.656	.269	.424	.092
Wass _{idf} *	.748	.766	.678	.706	.687	.463	.412	.163
Entro_Wass _{tf} *	.692	.706	.615	.666	.640	.262	.422	.089
Entro_Wass _{idf} *	.745	.794	.675	.720	.683	.467	.425	.171
Systems that rely on cross-lingual embeddings								
nBOW _{tf}	.530	.490	.493	.464	.237	.121	.449	.217
nBOW _{idf}	.574	.546	.521	.502	.341	.179	.470	.267
Wass _{tf}	.744	.748	.660	.681	.404	.407	.582	.434
Wass _{idf} *	.778	.784	.703	.718	.507	.465	.620	.479
Entro_Wass _{tf} *	.753	.786	.677	.710	.424	.494	.582	.607
Entro_Wass _{idf} *	.799	.820	.717	.756	.523	.549	.620	.643
Handling OOV words & cross-lingual embeddings								
nBOW _{tf}	.518	.541	.426	.468	.193	.148	.635	.451
nBOW _{idf}	.653	.659	.597	.592	.407	.349	.693	.544
Wass _{tf}	.815	.836	.788	.801	.675	.435	.845	.731
Wass _{idf} *	.867	.869	.812	.837	.721	.599	.856	.786
Entro_Wass _{tf} *	.830	.856	.796	.812	.718	.555	.851	.816
Entro_Wass _{idf} *	.875	.887	.828	.855	.741	.695	.864	.850

Figure 1: The MRR scores achieved by the models

Following the samples provided in the source code, we will focus **only on reproducing some of the approaches** (the novel ones) and **using only the English-French bilingual dataset**.

5 CODE AND WORKFLOW

As mentioned before, there is a GitHub repository where the source code used for the implementation of this experiment is provided. When accessing this repository, one finds out that they only provide the source code for the implementation Wass and Entro_Wass methods. Although it would be ideal to be able to reproduce the implementation of the baselines too, we found acceptable the fact that they show only what is a novelty in this field.

The workflow proposed by the authors to reproduce the results is as follows:

1. Install the **packages** on which the implementation of these methods relies (<https://github.com/PythonOT/POT> Python Optimal Transport for calculating Wasserstein distances and <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/> Scikit-learn for extending the nearest neighbors classifier to provide a generic framework for using their method).
2. Run a help script to **download the Numberbatch embeddings** that they use in this paper. In this case, they provide a script to extract the embeddings for a subset on languages (English and French). This is done through the file `get_embeddings.sh` after cloning the repository. After running it, two files are created containing the English and French word embeddings respectively.
3. **Run the `emd.py` file** with several arguments (the two embeddings, the two datasets where retrieval is performed, the upper limit of words and the last one for the second language - by default the first one is English). This outputs the MRR scores of the implemented methods on these two datasets (both retrieving English documents given French queries and vice-versa) as well as different timings.

Although the source code only shows how to implement the experiment with two datasets, it would be easy to reproduce the results for the resting datasets. However, we will stick to these two in order to not make the reproducibility experiment too long and tedious.

Apart from this, information on how to parallelize the implementation of this method. A comparison on the timing of both Wass and Entro_Wass for different parallelization levels is also provided. As a good reproducibility practice reproducibility, the machine that they used for it is specified.

Given all this, part of the results gotten in **this paper should be able to be reproduced only by re-running few lines of code**. However, this will not be as simple as it may seem. In the next section, the most important difficulties encountered will be detailed.

6 DIFFICULTIES

When trying to recreate the experiment, we ran into several problems. Some of which we sadly didn't manage to figure out before the deadline of this task.

6.1 Required packages

Within the file `get_embeddings.sh`, the method `wget` is used to access the data. However, they do not specify that `wget` should be installed in the machine and added to the environmental path. In this way, the installation other packages apart from `sklearn` and `POT` was needed. We could only figure that out when going through the code or due to raising errors within execution.

6.2 Versioning

Neither in the paper nor in the Github repository, are the system specifications documented. We therefore had to do quite a bit of experimenting with figuring out which packages were used. Syntax hinted us at using python 2 (ended with 2.7), and by looking at parameters for the various functions, we were able to dial in which versions of the packages were required. For instance `sklearn.metrics.scorer` modules is used, which was deprecated in version 0.22, leading us to the conclusion that a prior package was used. similarly a module that was added after 0.17 was used, so we were in a range between 0.17 and 0.22. This backtracking was done for every package, until the code was running.

6.3 Retrieval of full dataset

Although the authors of the paper[5] offers a small data-subset (English-French) available on their Github, we wanted to try to recreate the full results according to the paper. our first, novel, approach was to modify `extract_embeddings_conceptNet.py` and rerun `get_embeddings.py` This gave us the additional embeddings files, but we were still lacking the text-corpora. In the paper, this is described as:

To construct the Wikipedia excerpts, we use the comparable Wikipedia corpora of linguatools[2] Following [23], the inter-language links are the golden standard...

When trying to backtrack, in order to recreate the full dataset for the remaining languages, we followed the paper[13] (reference [23] in the original paper). This paper in turn references other repositories. Specifically it references the data being available at [9], but this site is no longer available. It also references the site [8], which no longer seems to have the dataset in question.

All Wikipedia articles for all experiments are downloaded from Wikipedia dumps: <http://dumps.wikimedia.org/>
These datasets are available online:
<http://people.cs.kuleuven.be/~ivan.vulic/software>

Next we tried to follow their references from paper[5]:

To generate the dictionaries for each language pair we use Wiktionary and, in particular, the open implementation of [1, 2].

The paper [3] references [2]. From this we finally found a promising repository at [4]. However, this didn't run on our system either, and deadline was fast approaching, so we chose to focus on **english-french**, as given in the original paper.

6.4 Divide by zero

WMD-tfidf gives a bunch of Divide By Zero errors, but runs non-the-less. As it was a fairly low amount of errors, and it didn't seem to throw the results quite off, we didn't look further into this.

6.5 Inability to produce all results

Only a small subset of the total measured results we were able to reproduce. The remaining results (the baselines) are not documented how they reach them. However, as the seen in the next section, the key results match the expected results, and thus it is highly plausible that the baseline is also within bounds.

The other languages were not tested.

7 KEY FINDINGS

From our results, we can see that the values of entropic regularized Wasserstein distance (also known as Sinkhorn distance) is higher compared to WMD. We know that a higher value signify higher Mean Reciprocal rank. Hence Sinkhorn has a clear superiority over WMD.

This proves that using regularization in the OT problem improves the performance and is faster, GPU-friendly and more accurate.

As we can see from the results table, both approaches benefit from the tfidf weighting scheme. Hence we can confirm tfidf is the better weighting scheme.

8 REPRODUCING

As python 2.7 was used in the code, we created a virtual environment to install python 2.7 since we had a higher version of python.

We had to backtrack a lot, in order to find the correct package versions. We narrowed it down to functioning with the following:

- Cython==0.29.21
- editdistance==0.5.3
- gyp==0.1
- joblib==0.14.1
- nltk==3.0.0
- numpy==1.16.6
- pathos==0.2.7
- POT==0.7.0
- scikit-learn==0.20.4

In addition, these packages were also used, although no backtracking was necessary, in order to make the code run:

- click==7.1.2
- dill==0.3.3
- multiprocessing==0.70.11.1
- pox==0.2.9
- ppft==1.6.6.3
- regex==2020.11.13
- scipy==1.2.3
- sklearn==0.0
- tqdm==4.55.1

9 OUR RESULTS

9.1 Performance

In the code documentation[6] there is a graph showing performance on an Intel Xeon system, and how the amount of cores effects runtime performance. E.g. for 12 cores it takes roughly 200 seconds according to the documentation. Rest of their system is not documented, so there is likely some differences. However when running on a fairly powerful computer; see appendix A.2, we get performance that is orders of magnitude worse:

```
real 175m11,750s
user 660m31,473s
sys 1328m40,037s
```

Figure 2: Run Performance

9.2 Results

When using the dataset that was uploaded on github[6], we were able to produce the following MRR results, which are in line with the results specified in the original paper.

Algorithm		EN → FR	FR → EN
WMD	tfidf	0.785	0.777
Sinkhorn	tfidf	0.820	0.798
WMD	tf	0.749	0.743
Sinkhorn	tf	0.785	0.753

Table 2: MRR for various algorithms when rerunning

10 STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE

As the proposed algorithm is deterministic, no need for cross validation, seeds, and similar considerations need to be considered. Despite the paper not stating statistical significance for their results, and we didn't reproduce this, due to not having access to baseline results, it's trivial to see that an MMR accuracy increase of 25%-50% depending on measures is a non-trivial increase, given the large size of the corpora.

11 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the authors of the paper did a great job at documenting algorithm, code, and data. They even made code and (parts of) data publicly available. However, as only the proposed algorithm is publicly available, we were unable to reproduce their baseline, and lack of proper Data Management/Citation, makes it cumbersome to try the validity of the proposed solution on new data. Getting the Wikipedia corpora is likely still possible, however it was not nearly as trivial a task, as we had anticipated. Finally, lack of wrapping the solution into a container/virtual machine also made it tough to replicate their results.

Irregardless of our challenges, we got partly results, and with these results, we can confirm that the proposed algorithm indeed performs as claimed in the paper.

11.1 Further works

We discussed publishing our results in [1]. However, we agreed that much work is left, before this paper is ready for publications. With deadline fast approaching, and multiple exams, we sadly had to let this go for now, and instead mention future works:

- Wrap entire solution in a container (e.g. Docker), for package stability
- Retrieve/regenerate the full dataset for all languages.
- **PRIMAD** Model.
- Proper Data Management & Citation.
- Reproduce and compare the remaining measures.
- Refactoring the code to Python3.
- Figure out why the performance-discrepancy is so huge between our implementation and [5].

REFERENCES

- [1] 43rd EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON INFORMATION RETRIEVAL. 2021. ECIR2021 Call for Reproducibility Track papers. Retrieved January 22, 2021 from <https://www.ecir2021.eu/call-for-reproducibility-track/>
- [2] Judit Ács. 2014. Pivot-based multilingual dictionary building using Wiktionary. (2014), 1938 – 1942.
- [3] Judit Acs, Katalin Pajkossy, and András Kornai. 2013. Building basic vocabulary across 40 languages. (2013), 52 – 58.
- [4] Judit Acs, Katalin Pajkossy, and András Kornai. 2014. wikt2dict Github. Retrieved January 21, 2021 from <https://github.com/juditacs/wikt2dict>
- [5] Georgios Balikas, Charlotte Laclau, Ievgen Redko, and Massih-Reza Amini. 2018. Cross-Lingual Document Retrieval Using Regularized Wasserstein Distance. In *Advances in Information Retrieval*, Gabriella Pasi, Benjamin Piwowarski, Leif Azzopardi, and Allan Hanbury (Eds.). Springer International Publishing, Cham, 398–410.
- [6] Georgios "Balikas, Charlotte Laclau, Ievgen Redko, and Massih-Reza" Amini. 2018. Wasserstein For Documents Github. Retrieved January 21, 2021 from <https://github.com/balikasg/WassersteinRetrieval>
- [7] Manash Pratim Barman, Kavish Dahekar, Abhinav Anshuman, and Amit Awekar. 2019. It's only Words and Words Are All I Have. In *Advances in Information Retrieval*, Leif Azzopardi, Benno Stein, Norbert Fuhr, Philipp Mayr, Claudia Hauff, and Djoerd Hiemstra (Eds.). Springer International Publishing, Cham, 30–36.
- [8] Croudsourced. 2013. Wikipediadumps. Retrieved January 21, 2021 from <http://dumps.wikimedia.org/>
- [9] Anne Elk. 2013. A Theory on Brontosaurus. Retrieved January 21, 2021 from <http://people.cs.kuleuven.be/~ivan.vulic/software/>
- [10] Michael Fell and Caroline Sporleder. 2014. Lyrics-based Analysis and Classification of Music. In *Proceedings of COLING 2014, the 25th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: Technical Papers*. Dublin City University and Association for Computational Linguistics, Dublin, Ireland, 620–631. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/C14-1059>
- [11] Juliana Freire, Norbert Fuhr, and Andreas Rauber. 2016. Reproducibility of Data-Oriented Experiments in e-Science (Dagstuhl Seminar 16041). *Dagstuhl Reports* 6, 1 (2016), 108–159. <https://doi.org/10.4230/DagRep.6.1.108>
- [12] Natali Ruchansky, Sungyong Seo, and Yan Liu. 2017. CSF: A Hybrid Deep Model for Fake News Detection. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM on Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (Singapore, Singapore) (CIKM '17)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 797–806. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3132847.3132877>
- [13] Ivan Vulić, Wim De Smet, Jie Tang, and Marie-Francine Moens. 2015. Probabilistic topic modeling in multilingual settings: An overview of its methodology and applications. *Information Processing and Management* 51, 1 (2015), 111 – 147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2014.08.003>

A APPENDICES

A.1 Code to make it run

```
1038 cd tuWien/
1040 cd 188992_Experiment_Design_for_Data_Science/
1042 cd assignments/
1044 mkdir assignment2
1045 cd assignment2/
1047 git clone https://github.com/balikasg/WassersteinRetrieval
1048 cd WassersteinRetrieval/
1051 bash get_embeddings.sh
1057 vim emd.py
1061 curl -O https://bootstrap.pypa.io/get-pip.py
1062 sudo python2.7 get-pip.py
1063 pip2.7 install scipy
1072 pip2.7 install numpy cython
1075 sudo apt-get install gcc python-dev
1077 pip2.7 install POT editdistance sklearn pathos nltk
1089 pip2.7 install nltk==3.0
1099 pip install POT editdistance sklearn pathos
1111 python -m nltk.downloader stopwords
1113 python -m nltk.downloader punkt
#### Did some rewriting, but SKLEARN has changed how the fit function works, so doesn't work in python3 yet
1117 history
```

A.2 system

Our testing was run on following system

```
$ lsb_release -a
```

```
Distributor ID: Ubuntu
```

```
Description: Ubuntu 20.04.1 LTS
```

```
Release: 20.04
```

```
$ python2.7 --version
```

```
Python 2.7.18
```

```
$ sudo lshw -short
```

```
H/W path    Class      Description
=====
          system  20QN0034MX (LENOVO_MT_20QN_BU_Think_FM_ThinkPad P53)
/0/3        memory    128GiB System Memory
/0/f        memory    384KiB L1 cache
/0/10       memory    1536KiB L2 cache
/0/11       memory    12MiB L3 cache
/0/12       Processor Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-9850H CPU @ 2.60GHz
/0/13       memory    128KiB BIOS
/0/100      bridge    8th Gen Core Processor Host Bridge/DRAM Registers
/0/100/1    bridge    Xeon E3-1200 v5/E3-1500 v5/6th Gen Core Processor PCIe Controll
/0/100/1/0  display   TU106GLM [Quadro RTX 3000 Mobile / Max-Q]
/0/100/2    display   UHD Graphics 630 (Mobile)
/0/100/4    generic   Xeon E3-1200 v5/E3-1500 v5/6th Gen Core Processor Thermal Subsy
/0/100/8    generic   Xeon E3-1200 v5/v6 / E3-1500 v5 / 6th/7th/8th Gen Core Processo
```